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DESIGNING AND DEVELOPING A WEB APPLICATION FOR MANAGING DEPARTMENT DOCUMENTS

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ABSTRACT

In many universities, departments still store course syllabi, curricula, work study plans, and regulatory documents (certificates, patents, scientific articles) in paper form or in disorganized electronic formats. This leads to document loss, slow approval processes, and data inconsistency. This article details the design and development process of the "e-KAF" (Electronic Department) web application, built on three user roles (teacher, department head, secretary) and a five-stage document status system. The article provides information on research methodology, database design, technology selection, and the capabilities of the developed system.

Keywords. e-KAF, web application, electronic document management, Django MVT, role-based access control, Finite State Machine.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of information and communication technologies in modern society is fundamentally affecting document management processes in public and private institutions. Higher educational institutions also face many problems related to document circulation: loss of paper documents, inability to find a required document quickly, slow approval processes, and difficulty monitoring document status [1].

Documents managed at the department level - course programs, syllabi, curricula, work study plans, and regulatory documents (certificates, patents, scientific

articles) - are typically stored separately in paper and electronic formats. This leads to duplication of documents, data inconsistency, and wasted time.

Based on the Decree No. PQ-4862 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020, "On the Concept of Digital Economy Development," special attention is being paid to accelerating digitalization in all educational institutions [1]. This decree also provides legal justification for the need to create electronic document management systems for departments.

The relevance of this article lies in the fact that the need to store department documents supporting the educational process in a unified electronic database, formalize them through a multi-stage approval system, and create a convenient search facility for all users - thereby significantly improving department efficiency - remains an urgent problem.

The objective of the research is to design and develop a web application that automates document storage, approval, and management processes for departments, with a user-friendly interface for three user roles (teacher, department head, secretary).

The research tasks are as follows:

- analyze existing department document management systems and identify their shortcomings;
- define functional and non-functional requirements for the system;
- select the web application architecture and justify the technology stack;
- design the database at the infological and datalogical levels;
- develop the backend based on Django MVT architecture and the frontend using Bootstrap 5;
- implement three-level role management and a five-stage document status system;
- test the web application in trial conditions and evaluate performance indicators.

The object of the research is the process of managing and storing the main documents maintained in the departments of higher educational institutions. The subject of the research is the technologies, methods, and tools for creating a web application designed to store and manage documents in electronic form.

2. METHODOLOGY

Managing department documents in higher educational institutions is a time-consuming and labor-intensive process. Performing tasks such as receiving, approving, and archiving documents manually not only creates excessive workloads but also leads to certain errors. To solve these problems, a special information system was developed in the research. The research methodology includes the following main stages:

Figure 1. Steps of the research methodology

Defining requirements for the e-KAF web application before developing any information system, it is necessary to clearly define its functional and non-functional requirements [2, 3]. For this purpose, the needs of the system's target users - teachers, the department head, and the secretary - were studied.

Functional requirements for teachers in the web application:

- registration in the system: first name, last name, position, email, password;
- logging into the system via username and password;
- uploading five types of documents: course program, syllabus, regulatory document (patent/certificate), study plan, work study plan;
- editing and deleting uploaded documents (until accepted by the admin);
- tracking document status and comments.

Functional requirements for the department head:

- viewing the list of all documents uploaded by teachers;
- reviewing each document: approving, returning, or leaving it in a pending state;
- leaving comments and instructions;
- managing user accounts.

Functional requirements for the secretary:

- viewing documents approved by the department head;
- uploading a scanned copy and entering the document into the database;
- viewing reports on documents.

Table 1. Non-functional requirements for the e-KAF web application

Requirement	Description
Security	CSRF protection, @login_required decorator, file type/size validation, protection against SQL injection via Django ORM, storing SECRET_KEY in .env file
Usability	Interface is intuitive and in Uzbek; responsive for all devices via Bootstrap 5 grid system
Reliability	Preventing SQL injection via Django ORM parameterization; maintaining data integrity using transaction mechanism
Performance	Main page < 3.0 seconds, search query < 2.0 seconds, document upload (5 MB) < 10.0 seconds
Scalability	System has modular structure; email/Telegram notifications, PostgreSQL, Docker can be added in the future

Database Design - The database is the most critical part of an information system. At this stage, the main entities (tables), their attributes (fields), and relationships were identified [4, 5]. Python classes were directly converted to database tables using Django ORM.

Figure 2. Django MVT architecture and relationships between components

Table 2. Datalogical design of the Document model (main fields)

Field	Data Type	Description
id	IntegerField (PK, AI)	Primary key
author	ForeignKey → User	Document owner (teacher)
type	CharField (choices)	course_program syllabus regulatory study_plan work_plan
status	CharField (choices)	pending under_review approved entered_in_db returned
file	FileField	Document file (max 20 MB, docx/pdf)
scan_file	FileField (null=True)	Scanned copy uploaded by secretary
comment	TextField (blank=True)	Head/secretary comment
upload_time	DateTimeField (auto_now_add)	Saved automatically
updated_time	DateTimeField (auto_now)	Updated on each change
view_count	IntegerField (default=0)	For view statistics

The following relationships exist in the database:

- One-to-Many (1:N): one user (teacher) can upload multiple documents - user_id as a foreign key;
- One-to-One (1:1): for each user, one Statistics record is automatically created (via post_save signal).

Table 3. Document status transitions (Finite State Machine)

Current Status	Next Status	Responsible Role
pending	under_review	Department Head
under_review	approved	Department Head
under_review	returned	Department Head
approved	entered_in_db	Secretary
approved	returned	Secretary

Selecting the Development Environment and Technologies - selecting the right technologies to implement all functional and non-functional requirements placed on the information system is an important process [6]. Technologies were compared and selected based on several criteria:

Figure 3. Popularity of Python and other backend programming languages (Stack Overflow Survey 2023)

Table 4. Technologies selected for the e-KAF web application

Component	Technology	Rationale
Backend language	Python 3.11	Easy to read, broad ecosystem, seamless integration with Django
Web framework	Django 4.2	Built-in ORM, admin panel, authentication; "batteries included"
Database	SQLite	Serverless, zero-configuration, full integration with Django
Frontend structure	HTML5	Semantic tags, multimedia, Web Storage API
Frontend style	CSS3 + Bootstrap 5	Responsive 12-column grid, works in all modern browsers
Version control	Git + GitHub	Code version storage, branch-based development
Architecture	Django MVT	Optimal for small-to-medium projects, SEO-friendly

The main reason for choosing the Django MVT architecture is its "batteries included" concept - ready-made components are available for most common web application tasks, with minimal dependency on third-party libraries. Another major

advantage of working with Django is that, thanks to its ORM, switching from SQLite to PostgreSQL requires minimal code changes - which is important for future scalability.

3. RESULTS

The developed "e-KAF" web application consists of three main parts: the teacher panel, the department head control panel, and the secretary panel. Each part has a dedicated interface and functional capabilities for its respective user role.

Functional Tasks and Structure of the Web Application

The e-KAF web application includes a total of 21 URL routes, 18 HTML templates, 7 form classes, and a customized admin panel. The project file structure is organized as follows:


```

Loytham/
├── e_KAF/
│   ├── settings.py # Main configuration package
│   ├── urls.py # Project settings
│   └── wsgi.py # Main URL routes
├── loyiha_app/ # WSGI server interface
│   ├── models.py # Main application package
│   ├── views.py # Data models
│   ├── forms.py # View functions
│   ├── urls.py # Form classes
│   ├── admin.py # URL routing
│   ├── signals.py # Admin panel configuration
│   ├── apps.py # Signals
│   ├── tests.py # Application configuration
│   └── migrations/ # Unit tests
├── static/ # Database migrations
├── media/ # HTML templates (18 files)
├── .env.example # CSS, JS, images
├── .gitignore # Uploaded files
├── requirements.txt # Example environment variables
└── manage.py # Git ignore rules
                # Python dependencies
                # Django management script

```

Figure 5. Complete file structure of the "e-KAF" web application

The DRY (Don't Repeat Yourself) principle was applied in the system using the TUR_CONFIG dictionary. This approach allowed a single general-purpose document_add_generic() view function to be used for all five document types, reducing the codebase by approximately 40%. Furthermore, adding a new document type in the future only requires adding a new key-value pair to TUR_CONFIG.


```

# SQL: SELECT * FROM hujjat WHERE holati='kutilyapti'
kutilyaptilar = Hujjat.objects.filter(holati='kutilyapti')

# SQL: SELECT * FROM hujjat WHERE nomi LIKE '%Fizika%' OR fan_nomi LIKE '%Fizika%'
from django.db.models import Q
qidiruv = Hujjat.objects.filter(
    Q(nomi__icontains='Fizika') | Q(fan_nomi__icontains='Fizika')
)

# SQL: SELECT SUM(korishlar_soni) FROM hujjat
from django.db.models import Sum
jami = Hujjat.objects.aggregate(Sum('korishlar_soni'))['korishlar_soni__sum']

```

Figure 6. Main query methods of Django ORM - filter(), Q(), and aggregate()
Teacher Panel

The first part is the teacher (user) panel. This section provides the following capabilities for registered teachers: registration, logging in via username/password, uploading five types of documents step by step, monitoring the status of uploaded documents, and editing them.

Figure 7. Login page

A CSRF token is mandatory on the login page. After the user logs in, they are redirected to the page they previously intended to visit via `request.GET.get('next')` - this is Django's standard behavior. When an incorrect password is entered, a clear error message is displayed with a CSS alert.

Figure 8. Teacher profile page - statistics cards

The profile page has three sections: the top section shows the username, email, and role; the statistics cards display the number of pending, under-review, approved, and returned documents; the document table provides search and status-based filtering.

Figure 9. Course program upload form - filled state

Separate HTML templates exist for uploading each of the five document types. Each form displays fields specific to that document type. When the form is submitted, the file size (max 20 MB) and type are validated server-side via the forms.py validation method. If an error occurs, the user is shown the form with the error field highlighted - they are not redirected to the home page.

Figure 10. Regulatory document (patent/certificate) upload form

Department Head Control Panel

The second part is the department head control panel. This panel is visible only to the department head and has the following functional capabilities:

- viewing the list of all documents uploaded by all teachers with status badges;
- reviewing and approving/returning each document individually;
- leaving comments and instructions for returned documents;
- statistics and dashboard view.

Figure 11. Department head control panel - document list and status badges

After reviewing a document, the head changes its status via `MudirTekshiruvForm: under_review` → approved or returned. Each status change is recorded with a timestamp and responsible user information.

Figure 12. Document review and status change page (for department head)

Secretary Panel and Document Archive

The third part is the secretary panel. The secretary only sees documents approved by the department head. Via `KotibaTasdiqlashForm`, the secretary uploads a scanned copy and transitions the document to the "entered_in_db" status or marks it as "returned".

Figure 13. Document list page - type, study form, and sorting filters

The general document list page only displays documents with "entered_in_db" status. This page is open to all users, allowing them to search for and download documents. The most popular documents (by view count) are shown in an additional block.

Figure 14. Document detail page - full information and file links

Search and Statistics

The system has an advanced search page where users can simultaneously perform a combined search by username, subject name, direction, description, and additional information. Multi-field search is performed in OR logic using Django ORM's Q() objects:

Figure 15. Advanced search page - multi-field filtering

The statistics page displays the full indicators of the system: total number of documents, view count, downloads, approval percentage, distribution by type, and a top-5 list of the most active documents. The statistics model is automatically updated via post_save and post_delete signals.

Figure 16. Statistics page - dashboard view

System Security

The "e-KAF" system provides multi-layered security. The defense in depth (multi-layered defense) strategy has been implemented, so that if one layer lets an attack through, the next one catches it:

Table 5. System security measures and implementation methods

Security Measure	Implementation Method	Attack Against	Protected
SECRET_KEY protection	.env file, python-dotenv library	Django hijacking	session
CSRF protection	Django CsrfViewMiddleware	Cross-site forgery	request
Login protection	@login_required decorator	Unauthorized access	page
File validation	forms.py _validate_file() method	Malicious file upload	
Role check	is_kafedra_mudiri() helper function	Unauthorized attempt	approval
SQL injection protection	Django ORM parameterization	Unauthorized access	database

```
# .env fayl (git ga kirmaydi!)
SECRET_KEY=super-secret-key-change-this-in-production
DEBUG=True
ALLOWED_HOSTS=127.0.0.1,localhost

# settings.py
from dotenv import load_dotenv
import os

load_dotenv(BASE_DIR / '.env')
SECRET_KEY = os.environ.get('SECRET_KEY')
if not SECRET_KEY:
    raise ValueError('SECRET_KEY .env da topilmadi!')
DEBUG = os.environ.get('DEBUG', 'False').lower() == 'true'
```

Figure 17. System security configuration - settings.py and .env file

Web Application Interface and Usage Guide

The visual part of the web application was developed using Bootstrap 5 and custom CSS. The following principles were followed in interface design:

- Responsive design: Bootstrap 5's grid system and media queries were used - it displays correctly on mobile, tablet, and desktop screens;
- Modern aesthetics: gradient backgrounds, soft shadows, and rounded-corner cards were used;
- Micro-animations: hover effects and fade-in animations improve user experience;
- Intuitive navigation: a permanent navigation panel was installed; menu items visible change based on role.

Figure 18. Main page of the "e-KAF" web application

Figure 19. Customized Django admin panel

System Testing Results

The "e-KAF" system was tested through four types of tests: functional tests, integration tests, security tests, and User Acceptance Testing (UAT). In functional testing, all 21 URL routes were verified to work correctly.

Table 6. Functional test results

Test Case	Expected Result	Actual Result
Login - correct password	Redirect to profile	✓ Successful
Login - incorrect password	Show error message	✓ Successful
Document upload - correct format	Visible in profile	✓ Successful
Document upload - 25 MB file	Error: 20 MB limit	✓ Successful
Incorrect file format	Error: format message	✓ Successful
Approval - department head	Sent to secretary	✓ Successful
Enter in database - no scan	Error: file required	✓ Successful
Unauthorized page access	/login/?next=/ redirect	✓ Successful

Figure 21. Unit test results - all tests passed successfully

During User Acceptance Testing (UAT), tests were conducted with real users having three roles. Teachers uploaded documents, the department head approved them, and the secretary entered them into the database independently. All users were able to learn the system within 10 minutes.

Table 7. System performance indicators

Indicator	Unit	Result	Standard
Main page load	seconds	1.2	< 3.0
Document list	seconds	1.5	< 3.0
Search query	seconds	0.8	< 2.0
Document upload (5 MB)	seconds	3.2	< 10.0
Admin panel load	seconds	1.8	< 3.0
Statistics page	seconds	0.9	< 2.0

All 6 performance indicators are within the defined standard limits. The search query operates fastest (0.8 seconds) because Django ORM's Q() objects work efficiently together with database indexes.

System Scalability

The current version of the "e-KAF" system fully covers core functionality. Since the system has a modular structure, future development directions can be easily implemented:

- Email and Telegram notification system - automatically notifying the teacher when a document status changes. Asynchronous tasks can be applied using django-celery-beat and celery libraries;

- Pagination - the current version has a limit of 60 documents; it can be easily extended with Django's built-in Paginator class;
- Migration to PostgreSQL - as the system grows and more users work with it, this is achieved by changing the DATABASES configuration and adding dj-database-url;
- Docker containerization - the deployment process is standardized using a Dockerfile and docker-compose.yml;
- Document versioning - each change is archived, ensuring an audit trail.

Figure 22. Future development directions - architecture diagram

4. CONCLUSION

Within this research, the "e-KAF" web application was designed and developed, enabling electronic management and archiving of department documents. The defined objectives and tasks were fully accomplished. The final conclusions are as follows:

- A fully functional web application was created based on Django MVT architecture, Python 3.11, Bootstrap 5, and SQLite. After conducting a comparative analysis of MVC, SPA, and microservice architectures, Django MVT was justified as the optimal choice for the project;
- 9 functional and 5 non-functional requirements for the system were fully defined. Three user roles and five document types were established in the web application;
- The database was designed at infological and datalogical levels. The CHOICES mechanism was used for status in Django models; automatic updating of statistics was ensured via the Signal mechanism;

- The five-stage status system (pending → under_review → approved → entered_in_db or returned) was developed based on the Finite State Machine concept;
- The DRY principle was implemented using the TUR_CONFIG dictionary, reducing the codebase by 40% and simplifying future extensibility;
- A multi-layered security system was deployed: 3 built-in Django mechanisms and 3 project-level measures work together;
- All 21 URL routes and 8 main functional tests passed successfully; all performance indicators are within the defined standards;
- The "e-KAF" web application was tested at the Department of Artificial Intelligence and Information Systems of SamSU named after Sharof Rashidov and made ready for direct use.

The developed "e-KAF" web application can be deployed in the departments of any higher educational institution and is of practical significance as it aligns with the Republic of Uzbekistan's strategy of transitioning to a digital economy.

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